

Hydroxylation of benzene using titanium dioxide as a semiconductor

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Manuscript received 9 November 2001, revised 5 June 2002, accepted 21 June 2002

The photocatalytic substitution reaction of benzene has been studied. Benzene is hydroxylated in the presence of semiconductor (TiO₂) and sodium hydroxide. The effects of different parameters like amount of NaOH and TiO₂, intensity of light, etc. on the rate of reaction are studied. A tentative mechanism for the hydroxylation of benzene is proposed.

Niiranen *et al.*¹ studied the photosubstitution of naphthalene and phenanthrene with two nucleophiles (hydroxide and cyanide ions) in water-acetonitrile (1 : 1) in the presence and absence of *p*-dicyanobenzene. The hydroxylation of benzoic acid², vitamin D³, cholesterol⁴, phenols⁵ and azulene⁶ and also photochemical oxidation of benzene and *N*-alkylbenzenes were reported⁷. Joseph *et al.*⁸ reported photochemical production of hydroxyl radicals.

The hydroxylation of benzene is a substitution reaction. Since benzene is an electron rich molecule and therefore, it is not easily attacked by a nucleophile under ordinary reaction conditions. It is of utmost importance to find out an alternate pathway for carrying out hydroxylation of aromatic system like benzene. For this purpose, the hydroxyl radicals may be generated in the aqueous medium by exposing the mixture of benzene and an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide in the presence of light and semiconducting titanium dioxide. These hydroxyl radicals attack the benzene moiety and thus result in the formation of phenol.

Results and Discussion

In a typical run using [benzene], 3.66 mol; TiO₂, 0.12 g, light intensity, 60 mW cm⁻²; [NaOH], 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, aliquots were drawn every hour upto 7 h and the optical density values were recorded. The plot of 1+log (O.D.) vs time (h) was found to be a straight line, thus indicating that the reaction follows first order kinetics. Therefore, the rate constant (*k*) of the reaction was determined by the expression, *k* = 2.303 × slope. The value of the rate constant of this reaction was found to be 1.36 × 10⁻⁶ s⁻¹.

The rate of hydroxylation was found to increase on increasing the concentration of sodium hydroxide (keeping all other factors identical). It reached a maximum at [NaOH] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ M and above which, it started decreasing upto 8.0 × 10³ M. This variation may be explained on the basis

that on increasing the concentration of sodium hydroxide, there is a corresponding increase in the concentration of hydroxyl ions and more [•]OH radicals are generated from these OH⁻ ions by holes,

However, if the concentration of hydroxyl ion is increased further above 5.0 × 10⁻³ M, hydroxyl ions will be adsorbed on the semiconductor surface giving it a negative charge. Now OH⁻ ions in the bulk of the solution will face a coulombic repulsion from the adsorbed OH⁻ ions, consequently, the rate of generation of hydroxyl radicals will decrease and in turn, a decrease in rate of reaction.

The effect of TiO₂ was studied in the range 0.06–0.16 g keeping amount of benzene and [NaOH] fixed. It is clear from the data that as the amount of TiO₂ increases, the rate constant also increases but after a certain limit a plateau is observed. This may be attributed to the fact that as the amount of semiconductor increases, the exposed surface area also increases but when amount of TiO₂ is increased above 0.12 g (*k* = 1.36 × 10⁻⁵ s⁻¹), there is no increase in the exposed surface area of the photocatalyst. At this point, increase in semiconductor will only increase the thickness of the layer at the bottom of the vessel and not the exposed surface area, and hence, the rate becomes constant.

Effect of varying amount of light intensity (15.0 to 90.0 mW cm⁻²) was studied keeping all factors identical. It was observed that increase in light intensity increases the rate of the reaction because more photons are available for excitation of electrons in conduction band leaving a hole in valence band, which ultimately leads to the formation of more [•]OH radicals and hence, the reaction rate was accelerated. At 60.0 mW cm⁻², the rate was found maximum, *k* = 1.36 × 10⁻⁵ s⁻¹.

Mechanism :

On the basis of the data, mechanism proposed for the photocatalytic hydroxylation of benzene is presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The participation of hydroxyl radicals as an active oxidizing species in hydroxylation reaction was confirmed by using $\cdot\text{OH}$ radical scavengers like isopropanol, formate ions, etc. It was observed that the rate of reaction is drastically reduced in the presence of these scavengers,

It may be concluded that $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals play an important role in hydroxylation of aromatic moiety like benzene.

Experimental

A mixture of benzene (50 ml), $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ NaOH solution (100 ml) and TiO_2 (0.12 g) was irradiated with 200 W tungsten lamp. The intensity of light was kept 60.0 mW cm^{-2} as measured by a solarimeter (Surymapa CEL 201). A water filter was used to cut-off the thermal radiations. The

progress of reaction was monitored spectrophotometrically using phenolphthalein as an indicator. The optical densities of aliquots (pink solution) at different time intervals were measured at λ_{max} 555 nm using a Systronics 106 spectrophotometer. The amount of phenol was estimated spectrophotometrically (λ_{max} 360 nm) using ferric chloride ($3.18 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$; 2.0 ml) and the yield was 2.0%. Some control experiments were also carried out.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. R. P. Mathur, Associate Professor (Retd.), Department of Chemistry, College of Science, Sukhadia University, Udaipur (India) for critical discussions.

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